

ҚОРАҚАЛПОҒИСТОНДА
ФАН ВА ТАЪЛИМ

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ИЛИМ ҲӘМ ТӘЛИМ

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**IDENTIFICATION, DIAGNOSIS AND REHABILITATION OF CHILD VIOLENCE
SIGNS: SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS**

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Summary: *The article examines international norms and definitions of the socio-legal status of children in national legislation, theoretically substantiates the fact that children are a generation that ensures the continuity of social life as part of the population. It also scientifically analyzes the fact that violence against children occurs as a social phenomenon in society, factors and conditions that cause violence. In addition, the essence of "Mobbing", "Bullying", "Cybermobbing" and "Cyberbullying" as traditional forms of violence against children is revealed, and the author's approaches to preventing violence against children are highlighted.*

Keywords: *children, violence, sexual, psychological, physical and emotional violence, bullying, mobbing, hazing, cybermobbing, cyberbullying, child neglect.*

Introduction.

In determining and diagnosing the type, form, methods and manifestations of violence against a person, some aspects of violence against children and youth are distinguished. By person, we mean a person who has successfully passed the stage of socialization, has a special status, position, role and place in social groups and social classes, and has individual characteristics. Since children and young people have not fully passed these socialization processes, they cannot be called full-fledged individuals. The reason is that children and young people cannot fully express themselves as individuals in the society, using their limited social position in the society.

President Shavkat Mirziyoev says in this regard: "A child is a deposit in the hands of parents," say our great scholars. Today's life proves in every way that our children, their fate and future are really a great investment. If we do not give our children a proper upbringing, if we do not keep an eye on their behavior and mood every day, if we do not teach them science and technology, if we do not find a decent job, then we will lose this it [1.480] .

Results and Discussion

Implementation of the requirements of the Convention "On the Rights of the Child" to a full life, guaranteeing the rights of children provided for in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Family Code and other laws, ensuring that they grow into a physically, intellectually, mentally and spiritually mature generation, as well as for the years 2022-2026 One of the main tasks in the field is to effectively ensure the implementation of the tasks defined in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan.

By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 22, in 2019 year №PQ4296 "On additional measures to further strengthen the guarantees of children's rights". It was determined that changes and additions should be introduced and according to the law, the types of oppression and violence used against the child were also about its prevention [2].

By child abuse we mean cruelty to children, physical and emotional abuse, sexual abuse, neglect, indifference to them, trafficking in children, use of child labor, their health, survival, development or dignity. actions such as preventing them from happening can be cited. According to the World Health Organization, child abuse is a global problem with serious lifelong consequences [3].

The procedure for determining the status of a child in international legal documents was first established in the "Geneva Declaration of the Rights of the Child" dated November 26, in 1924 year. » is identified [4.14].

Article 1 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted by the United Nations on November 20, in 1989 year, states that "every person under the age of 18 years is considered a child if, according to the law applicable to the child, he or she has not reached the age of majority earlier [5].

In our national legislation, on January 7, in 2008 year, Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Children's Rights" states that "Child (children) is a person (persons) who have reached eighteen years of age (adulthood) [6].

In Uzbekistan, the initial work on the protection of children and ensuring the guarantees of children's rights began with the 757-XII accession to this convention on December 9, in 1992 year, with the decision of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Joining the Convention on the Rights of the Child" on December 9, in 1992 year [7].

As for the issue of youth, Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Policy Regarding Youth" dated November 20, in 1991 year defines youth as citizens between the ages of 14 and 30. This law was amended on September 14, in 2016 year, in which, although there were no changes in the age limit of young people, the concepts of young family, young professional youth entrepreneurship were included in this law [8].

In articles 3, 10 and 16 №-139 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 07, in 2008 year "On Guarantees of Children's Rights", it is possible to see the articles on the protection of children from various forms of violence. In particular, Article 3 of this law includes abused children in the group of children in need of social protection. Article 10 states that "The state ensures the privacy of the child's identity, home, and correspondence, and protects the child from all forms of exploitation and abuse, including physical, mental, and sexual abuse, torture, or other forms of cruel, harsh, or degrading treatment." implements protection from abuse, sexual harassment, involvement in committing crimes and antisocial acts" and Article 16 "From pornography, mass media that show cruelty and violence, insult human dignity, have a harmful effect on children and cause crimes to be committed use, distribution of literature and screening of films are prohibited" [9].

This law was adopted seventeen years after independence. However, it should also be noted that until now, the issue of violence against children has only been dealt with in the articles of the Criminal Code, Criminal Procedure Code and Code of Administrative Responsibility. This may restore the violated rights of the abused child. However, due to the lack of norms for the protection of children from such violence, in 2008 year, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Children's Rights" was adopted, and a separate law aimed at protecting children from various forms of violence and guaranteeing their rights was adopted in our country.

Due to the fact that the forms of violence against children have changed over time, this in 2008 year Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Children's Rights" was adopted in a new version on March 11, in 2020 year, with additions and amendments. With the adoption of the new version of this law, no changes or additions were made to the text of the articles that list the types of violence against children.

Reviewing the social history of violence against children in the family and society allows for a clearer understanding of the causes of this phenomenon and the essence of the problem, sociological analysis and synthesis of interpretations and views on violence against children. Is a part of population, the phenomenon of violence against children is one of the social evils in the society that has been going on for a very long time.

In our opinion, the initial view of studying the historical and sociological aspects of the problem of child abuse is to look at infant mortality from the initial stage of child abuse. It is known from the history of mankind that facts such as the deliberate killing of newborns in primitive societies or the execution of male infants as sacrifices to gods and goddesses, and the killing of children during food shortages indicate that the history of violence against children is very ancient.

In ancient Sparta, a special authority examined all newborns to determine their health and usefulness to society. As a result of such an examination, boys were found "unfit" to live, and

children born with physical defects and disabilities were sentenced to death. Also, in ancient Roman law, this condition strictly prohibited the raising of children with physical defects or disabilities in the family. It is a remarkable fact that even enlightened people such as Hippocrates and Soran of Ephesus, the founder of gynecology, discussed the question of which newborns deserve to be educated and educated [10. 447].

In ancient Roman law, children were considered the property of their parents, and until the child reached adulthood, it was considered an inferior being, the result of sexual relations, it was literally the property of the parents, mainly the father. This rule adopted from Roman law was called (*patria potestas* - strict parental authority), and the child was completely at the mercy of his parents. A father has the right to use his child as an employee, property, and use force and punishment at will.

In our opinion, the opposite of child cruelty in the West can be seen in the East. In particular, it is envisaged that the child should be given all the love of his parents so that he will be the successor of the generation and the owner of tomorrow. In Eastern countries, especially in Movarounnahr, China, Khorasan, Egypt, it is not important how a child is born, regardless of whether he is born healthy or with a physical defect, his status as a child has not changed and the child is not considered the property of the parents. A child is considered to be an object of socialization and a person in the future, as well as a being born with the right to live. We can find such situation in Avesta, Confucian views, Indian Vedas, Bible, Holy Quran and Hadith. In some Arab countries, violence against girls born in the period of pre-Islamic ignorance, such as burying alive and sacrificing boys to idols and idols, was completely eliminated with the introduction of Islam.

While some modern forms of child abuse and harassment are referred to as bullying, mobbing, hazing, cyberbullying and cybermobbing, these terms are generally used as synonyms for child abuse. Interpretation of these concepts from the point of view of sociology allows to distinguish their different aspects.

We considered it necessary to quote the following rule as an author's interpretation of the concept of violence against children. Child abuse is cruel treatment of a child, neglect of a child, lack of love in the relationship between a child and a parent, actions that harm the physical and mental health of the child, his development and peace of mind, as well as limit his rights or freedom, or It is inactivity caused by neglecting to provide housing and food necessary for development, health and growth, education, and living .

Child abuse also includes the concept of "Persecution", which is psychological or physical violence aimed at forcing children to submit to or leave the dominant group (leader) and its in-group laws. Such cases are mostly found in preschool educational institutions, schools, orphanages, family children's homes (Foster care), educational colonies, sports schools, hospitals, camps and also in various institutions where children stay. There are forms of harassment such as gossiping, slandering, scaring, isolating, insulting, humiliating, and coveting [11.147].

The English term child molestation is used as a universal term in sociology and social work as "Mobbing", "Bullying", "Hazing", "Cybermobbing" and "Cyberbullying". Bullying means belligerent, hooligan, bully, bully, bully, violent, and it is a repeated situation of violence and persecution by one person against a weak person who cannot defend himself [12.150].

Therefore, bullying is always aimed at harming the child, instilling fear in him, depressing him, humiliating him, subjugating him to himself. In educational institutions, bullying is a common phenomenon among peers, bullying is often perpetrated by older students against younger students. This type of bullying can also be used by teachers, staff or management of educational institutions. Bullying can also occur in the family between older and younger children, between adopted and foster children, and between children of the father or mother.

Mobbing (eng. mobbing - crowd) is a form of psychological violence in the form of mass persecution of a child by a large group of children in a community. In mobbing, those who cause harm are called mobbers, and those who are harmed are called "victims". The manifestation of

mobbing among young people and adults is different from that of children, and it is described as a kind of "Psychological terror" that involves regularly repeated hostile and unethical behavior of one person directed against another person. The forms of mobbing among young people and adults are manifested in the form of laughing at physical defects, isolation, denial, touching, pushing, making fun of clothes, not talking and who cannot defend himself. Bullying is distinguished from mobbing by the performance of a specific student or group of students who have the authority, rather than the whole class, in the role of the bully [12.151].

Hazing (eng. hazing) is the application of a series of tests by the leaders of the group hierarchy as conditions for the acceptance of a child into this group in order to become a member of a particular group. In hazing, probation conditions are considered child abuse. In this case, the child has to commit a crime, steal, do something against his will, run away from home or perform some phenomenal task. Such manifestations of hazing occur among neglected children, gangs of bullies, correctional institutions and children's organizations. The most negative aspect of hazing is that almost 70% of children who are victims of hazing violence die due to inexperience.

There are forms of cruel and violent treatment of children, such as physical, sexual, psychological violence and neglect of the child's needs, exploitation. Child abuse can be classified according to a number of parameters depending on the occurrence:

- overt or covert violence;
- violence related to the behavior of the abuser;
- current or past violence;
- violence lasting once or several times over many years [13.17].

Physical violence against children means harming the child's health by parents or their substitutes, guardians, sponsors, educators, teachers, coaches, nannies, caregivers, social worker assistants, group leaders or persons whose work activities are related to children. Its development is causing various injuries and injuries to the body that destroy physical and mental health. These actions include hitting, torturing, shaking, suffocating, putting in water, pulling hair, hitting with an object, slapping the face, burning with hot objects, pressing on smoked tobacco, sticking a needle, biting, giving psychotropic substances, drinking alcohol, eating it is manifested in the form of not giving, leaving naked, punishing the child for defecating, taking him outside on cold days, doing things the child cannot do, lifting heavy loads. It can also be done by scaring the child with various objects as a tool of humiliation [14.212].

Child sexual abuse is a form of cruel treatment of a minor child by an adult or another child by tricking or coercing them into sexual activities in order to satisfy their sexual needs or for financial gain. Child sexual abuse, sometimes referred to as "Pedophilia", is the attempt or coercion of a minor or sexually immature child to engage in sexual activity [15,195].

Psychological violence against children is constant or occasional verbal abuse, cursing, name-calling, forcing the child to act like an animal or human, forcing him to change his voice, making propaganda that confuses the child about his gender, threatening with various pictures and objects, not sleeping, sleeping a lot, humiliating, humiliating, stigmatizing, dressing contrary to gender, completely isolating the child from the outside world, forcing the child to realize himself as an animal rather than a human [16.101].

Emotional abuse of children is the neglect of the basic needs of the child by parents or their substitutes, and the lack of care for the child results in a disturbance of the child's emotional state and a danger to his health or development. This form of violence can also be described as moral cruelty.

Neglect of children (neglect) is a form of psychological abuse in which a person systematically ignores the vital needs of a dependent victim (child). Child neglect manifests itself in the following forms:

- neglect of food - depriving the child of food or malnutrition;
- carelessness in providing the child with clothes - dressing the child in clothes and shoes that do not correspond to the season or neglecting to dress the child at all;

neglect of hygiene - non-observance of general norms of personal hygiene, violation of the sanitary conditions of the residence that threaten the life or health of the child;

Negligence in medical care - lack or refusal of necessary medical care to protect the child's life, health and physical integrity, failure to vaccinate against various diseases on time, negligence to various disorders in the functioning of the child's internal and external organs, negligence to the fact that the child's body part has stopped developing and changes, rapid not to contact medical personnel in cases;

neglect of education - carelessness in sending the child to kindergarten and school for education and training, carelessness in the child's efforts to acquire school education;

emotional neglect - denial of the child's psychological and emotional problems by parents or their substitutes;

negligent supervision - negligence in unsupervised conditions or situations that could lead to illness, injury, disability or death of a child;

child exploitation is any form of forced labor that endangers a child's health, safety, morals, mental and physical development, including hinders his education. This is mainly manifested in the involvement of children in field work in agriculture, carrying goods, hiring a cart, feeding livestock, begging, cleaning, trading, and digging in mines [16.121].

Conclusions

In conclusion, the types and scope of violence against children are quite wide, and new methods of violence are emerging today. Although the types of child abuse are similar, the difference is that child abuse is committed only by adults. If there is violence between children, then children commit violence without consciously understanding the consequences. Violence against children, if committed by adults, is used for the purpose of getting rid of the child, making the child completely dependent on him, easily controlling the child, intimidating the child, using the child.

We believe that it is possible to prevent and eliminate all forms of violence against children in society. In order to prevent and eliminate violence, communicate with children and young people in a timely manner, strictly establish discipline in the educational masses, effectively organize the cooperative work of the neighborhood group, prevent the spread of alcohol, narcotic drugs, and psychotropic drugs among young people. , can be achieved by preventing the carrying of firearms and cold weapons by young people, protecting them from cyber threats and risks by constantly checking the phones, computers and tablets of children and young people, reducing poverty and ending poverty.

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Rezyume: Maqolada bolalarning ijtimoiy va huquqiy maqomlariga berilgan xalqaro normalar va milliy qomunchilikdagi ta'riflar sharhlar keltirilib bolalar aholining bir qismi sifatida ijtimoiy hayotning davomiyligini ta'minlovchi avlod ekanligi nazariy asoslantiriladi. Shuningdek, bolalarga nisbatan qo'llanilgan zo'ravonlik jamiyatda ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida ro'y berish=0s i, zo'ravonlikni keltirib chiqaruvchi omillar va sharoitlar ilmiy tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari bolalarga nisbatan qo'llanilgan zo'ravonlik an'anaviy ko'rinishlari sifatida «Mobbing», «Bulling», «Kibermobbing» va «Kiberbulling» ko'rinishlarining mohiyati ochib beriladi va bolalarga nisbatan zo'ravonlikni oldini olish borasida mualliflik yondashuvlar yoritilgan.

Резюме: В статье рассматриваются международные нормы и определения социально-правового положения детей в национальном законодательстве, теоретически обосновывается тот факт, что дети являются поколением, обеспечивающим непрерывность социальной жизни как часть населения. Также научно анализируется тот факт, что насилие в отношении детей происходит как социальное явление в обществе, факторы и условия, вызывающие насилие. Кроме того, раскрывается сущность «Моббинга», «Буллинга», «Кибермоббинга» и «Кибербуллинга» как традиционных форм насилия в отношении детей, а также освещаются авторские подходы к предотвращению насилия в отношении детей

Kalit so'zlar: bolalar, zo'ravonlik, jinsiy, psixologik, jismoniy va iqisodiy zo'ravonlik, bulling, mobbing, xeyzing, kibermobbing, kiberbulling, bolaga beparvo munosabat.

Ключевые слова: дети, насилие, сексуальное, психологическое, физическое и эмоциональное насилие, буллинг, моббинг, дедовщина, кибермоббинг, кибербуллинг, безнадзорность детей.